

Table 1. Effect of cold temperature and low light on the export and distribution of photosynthetic products of ^{14}C (^{14}C supplied before treatment with cold temperature and low light). Guangzhou, China.

Organ	^{14}C content					
	Control ^a (natural condition)			Treated ^a with cold temp and low light		
	cpm/50 mg	Total cpm	%	cpm/50 mg	Total cpm	%
Flag leaf	4,497 ± 637	18,263	4.8	6,039 ± 795	23,953	1.8
Flag leaf sheath	2,091 ± 402	13,327	3.5	1,636 ± 346	8,630	6.6
Functional leaf blade	1,039 ± 934	10,993	2.9	20 ± 11	197	0.2
Functional leaf sheath	954 ± 303	9,571	2.5	32 ± 12	292	0.2
Panicle	5,703 ± 1,299	99,118	26.3	4,358 ± 2,113	52,304	40.3
Stem	3,490 ± 1,716	68,830	18.2	2,540 ± 1,040	43,609	33.6
Root	9,999 ± 4,216	157,369	41.7	44 ± 1.5	712	0.6
Total cpm in rice plant		377,471	100		129,697	100

^acpm = counts per minute (radioactive isotope intensity).

decreased the root's activities and photosynthetic products. From these results, we can deduce that the root is damaged more seriously than the other organs

are.

The total ^{32}P content and the content per 50 mg in each organ affected by cold temperature and low light, except the

Table 2. Effect of cold temperature and low light on the absorption and distribution of ^{32}P in the rice plant. Guangzhou, China.

Organ	^{32}P (com/50 mg)	
	Control (natural conditions)	Treated with cold temp and low light
Leaf blade	438 ± 33	434 ± 49
Leaf sheath	399 ± 31	428 ± 103
Stem	365 ± 21	361 ± 61
Panicle	436 ± 61	138 ± 6

panicle, were almost the same as those in the control organs (Table 2). The ^{32}P content in the treated panicles was 31.6% that in the control panicles, which indicates that cold temperature and low light impeded the translocation of ^{32}P from roots to panicles. That illustrates that cold temperature and low light can greatly harm panicle growth. ■

Measuring the tensile strength of japonica-indica hybrid rices in Korea

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In Korea, about 76% of the paddy fields are planted to japonica-indica hybrid rices.

The rice spikelet's tensile strength at harvest was measured in japonica-indica hybrid rices and compared with that in japonica rices. The abscission layer between the pedicel and the rachilla of the spikelet also was studied.

The japonica-indica rices generally had lower tensile strength than the japonica rices (see table). Yushin had the lowest tensile strength (98 g), and Milyang 21 had the highest (188 g). However, Milyang 21 had lower strength than Nongbeak, which had the lowest value among the japonica recommended rice varieties. Akibare had the highest tensile strength among the japonica-type rices tested.

In the japonica-indica varieties Yushin and Milyang 21, the parenchymatous cells of the abscission layer, which extends from the epidermis to near the central vascular tissue in the pedicel, collapsed (see figure). In the japonica Jojeongjo, however, the parenchymatous cells did not collapse and in Akibare, also a japonica, the abscission

Degree of grain shedding of the recommended rice varieties in Korea.

Variety	Tensile strength (g) ± S.D.
<i>Japonica-indica hybrid rice</i>	
Yushin	98 ± 32.9
Suwon 258	100 ± 29.0
Suwon 251	107 ± 33.8
Milyang 23	119 ± 36.0
Nopoong	131 ± 38.5
Joseng tongil	133 ± 34.1
Rekyeong	134 ± 35.4
Tongil-chal	142 ± 35.4
Yeongnamjoseng	147 ± 34.6
Iri 326	156 ± 33.0
Milyang 30	165 ± 38.2
Suwon 264	183 ± 38.6
Milyang 21	188 ± 30.7
<i>Japonica rice</i>	
Nongbeak	195 ± 32.7
Satominori	226 ± 43.9
Palkeum	237 ± 47.9
Akibare	245 ± 42.9
Jinheung	245 ± 51.0
Jojeongjo ^a	94 ± 34.0

^aLocal variety in old time.

layer could not be found.

The results show that the abscission layer of the japonica-indica hybrid rices in Korea is the same as that of indica rice. ■

Micrographs of longitudinal sections of the abscission layer in Yushin (top), Milyang 21 (second), Jojeongjo (third), and Akibare (bottom). Note the difference in collapse of the cells of the abscission layer (A). V = vascular tissue.

